

Predicting Condition Rating of Concrete Bridge Decks

Hadil Helaly¹, Khaled El-Rayes^{*1}, and Ernest-John Ignacio¹

¹Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL 61801.

*Corresponding Author: Khaled El-Rayes, Email: elrayes@illinois.edu

Abstract:

The objective of this study is to develop five machine learning models for predicting the condition ratings of cast-in-place and precast concrete bridge decks across the United States in order to support decision-makers in prioritizing bridge maintenance actions. The models were developed in four main steps that focused on collecting historical bridge records from the National Bridge Inventory (NBI); preparing collected data to guarantee its quality and reliability; training predictive models using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), LASSO Regression (LR), Ridge Regression (RR), Random Forest Regressor (RFR), and Gradient Boosting (GB) algorithms; and evaluating and validating the performance of the developed models. Performance evaluation results using the training dataset showed that the GB model achieved the highest coefficient of determination (R^2) values of 94.06%. The results of the validation analysis using the testing dataset indicated that the RFR model outperformed the others in terms of Mean Absolute Percentage Error of 6.29% and Mean Absolute Error of 0.39, while the GB model achieved the lowest median absolute error of 0.24. Both the RFR and GB models achieved the lowest root mean square error of 0.57. The developed models provide transportation agencies with robust and generalizable tools for predicting bridge deck condition ratings, enabling improved maintenance prioritization and more effective, data-driven infrastructure management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) reported that approximately 56% of the United States bridges are in fair or poor condition and the American Road and Transportation Builder Association (ARTBA) estimates that addressing needed bridge repairs would cost more than \$319 billion (ARTBA 2023; FHWA 2024). These statistics underscore the urgent need for data-driven models to support the prioritization of bridge maintenance and rehabilitation. Several studies have been conducted to support decision-makers and bridge planners in this challenging task by developing models to predict bridge condition ratings. For example, Huang (2010) developed a model for predicting the condition and deterioration of Wisconsin bridges. Chyad and Abudayyeh (2020) developed a predictive deterioration model for Michigan's concrete bridge decks. Althaqafi and Chou (2022) estimated deterioration rates for Ohio's bridge components such as decks, superstructures, and substructures. Despite the contributions of these studies, existing models are typically developed using data from a single state, which limits their ability to capture the variability in environmental conditions, traffic patterns, and maintenance practices across the United States. Accordingly, their applicability and predictive performance are often limited when applied to other regions.

2. METHODOLOGY

The main objective of this study is to develop novel machine learning models to accurately predict the condition rating of cast-in-place and precast concrete bridge decks. This was achieved in four main steps that focused on: (1) gathering historical data for both cast-in-place and precast concrete bridge decks; (2) preparing collected data to guarantee its quality and reliability; (3) developing machine learning models for estimating concrete deck condition ratings; and (4) evaluating the performance of the developed models, as shown in Figure 1. The following sections provide description of each of these four model development steps.

Figure 1. Development steps of machine learning models

2.1 Data Collection

This step focused on identifying and collecting all data influencing bridge deck condition ratings and deterioration that are available in the National Bridge Inventory (NBI) database (FHWA 2025). The database contains data on 624,194 bridges across all 50 U.S. states, with 108 items recorded for each bridge.

Although the database includes bridge records from 1697 to 2024, the data collected in this task focused on bridges that were constructed since 1960 to ensure their relevance to existing bridges. Of these bridges, 60% are concrete cast-in-place deck bridges, 11% are precast concrete deck bridges, 20% are culverts, and 9% utilize other deck materials such as timber, steel, or aluminum. Since the scope of this study is limited to predicting the condition ratings of concrete deck bridges, only cast-in-place and precast concrete bridges were considered. Accordingly, the collected dataset includes 286,034 bridge records.

Based on a comprehensive literature review (Assaad and El-Adaway 2020; Bolukbasi et al. 2004; Nasab and Elzarka 2023; Srikanth and Arockiasamy 2020; Tolliver et al. 2011; Winoto and Roy 2023), 31 data items were identified to have an impact on the deck condition rating. These items can be categorized into 7 main groups: location, time, dimensions, condition ratings, traffic, service and classification, and other/protection, as shown in Table 1. Some of these items are directly incorporated into the predictive models, while others are used to generate derived variables. For example, the bridge age is calculated based on its construction and maintenance history, as shown in Eq. (1) and (2).

$$\text{IF Type of Work} == \text{Bridge or Deck Replacement:} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Bridge Age} = \text{Date of Inspection} - \max(\text{Year Built}, \text{Year Reconstructed}, \text{Year of Improvement})$$

$$\text{Else:} \tag{2}$$

$$\text{Bridge Age} = \text{Date of Inspection} - \max(\text{Year Built}, \text{Year Reconstructed})$$

Table 1. Collected data from NBI database

Category	Fields
Location	State Code
Time	Year Built, Year of Improvement, Year Reconstructed, Date of Inspection, Inspection Frequency (Months)
Dimensions	Approach Width (m), Max Span Length (m), Structure Length (m), Deck Width (m), Deck Area (m ²), Main Unit Spans (count), Degrees of Skew
Condition Ratings	Deck Condition, Superstructure Condition, Substructure Condition, Channel Condition
Traffic	ADT (Average Daily Traffic), % ADT Trucks
Service & Classification	Service On, Service Under, Structure Kind (Material), Structure Type, Deck Structure Type, Approach Kind, Approach Type, Design Load
Other / Protection	Work Proposed, Surface Type (Protective System), Membrane Type, Deck Protection

2.2 Data Preparation

This step focused on preparing the raw data that was collected in the previous phase to ensure its quality and usability and was achieved in five main substeps. First, the deck condition rate (ranging from 1 = poor to 9 = excellent) was defined as the predicted variable, and 23 predictor variables were identified to have a potential impact on deck condition rating, as shown in Figure 2. Second, the identified predictor variables were categorized into numerical variables that represent measurable quantities such as deck length and width, and categorical variables that represent attributes with discrete values such as deck type that can be classified as concrete cast-in-place or precast concrete (Helaly et al. 2025a), as shown in Figure 2. Third, the dataset was cleaned by identifying and removing outliers to improve model performance and reduce noise, resulting in the removal of 20,587 bridge records. Fourth, the categorical and numerical variables were transformed to enhance the performance of the machine learning models using the min-max normalization technique for all numerical variables, and the one hot encoding method for all categorical variables (Daly et al. 2016; Hardy 1993; Helaly et al. 2025b). Fifth, the transformed data were divided into training and testing sets that include 80% and 20% of the cleaned dataset, respectively.

Figure 2. Predictor and predicted variables

2.3 Model Development

This step focused on the development of five ML models that can be used to estimate the condition rating of cast-in-place and precast concrete bridge decks. These models were developed using five ML algorithms that are widely used for this type of prediction including Ordinary Least Square (OLS), LASSO Regression (LR), Ridge Regression (RR), Random Forest Regressor (RFR), and Gradient Boosting (GB). Each model was trained using the training set identified in the previous phase.

2.4 Model Evaluation

This step focused on evaluating and validating the performance of the developed ML models using the training and testing datasets, respectively. First, the performance of the developed models was evaluated using the training dataset by analyzing their coefficient of determination (R^2) values. This analysis indicates that the Gradient Boosting (GB) model achieved the highest performance with R^2 values of 94.06%, as shown in Table 2. Second, the performance of the developed ML models was validated using the testing dataset by comparing their predicted values to the true values. This validation analysis was conducted using four primary metrics: mean absolute percentage error ($MAPE$), mean absolute error (MAE), median absolute error ($MedAE$), and root mean squared error ($RMSE$). The results show that the Random Forest Regressor (RFR) model outperformed the other models in two metrics of mean absolute percentage error ($MAPE = 6.29\%$), mean absolute error ($MAE = 0.39$), while the Gradient Boosting (GB) model outperformed other developed models in median absolute error ($MedAE = 0.24$). Both RFR and GB achieved the lowest RMSE value of 0.57 ($RMSE = 0.57$), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Performacne evaluation of developed ML models

Developed ML Algorithms	Training Dataset	Testing Dataset			
	R^2 (%)	$MAPE$ (%)	MAE (CR)	$MedAE$ (CR)	$RMSE$ (CR)
Ordinary Least Square	47.8	7.51	0.47	0.35	0.63
LASSO Regression	47.8	7.47	0.46	0.34	0.62
Ridge Regression	49.04	7.90	0.48	0.36	0.66
Random Forest Regressor	93.43	6.29	0.39	0.25	0.57
Gradient Boosting	94.06	6.36	0.40	0.24	0.57

*Bold text highlights best performing ML models

3. CONCLUSION

Five machine learning (ML) models were developed to assist bridge planners in predicting the condition rating of cast-in-place and precast concrete bridge decks. The models were developed in four main steps that focused on collecting historical bridge records from the National Bridge Inventory (NBI); preparing collected data to ensure quality and reliability; training the ML models using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), LASSO Regression (LR), Ridge Regression (RR), Random Forest Regressor (RFR), and Gradient Boosting (GB); and evaluating and validating model performance. The evaluation results showed that the GB model achieved the highest performance on the training dataset. The validation results indicated that the RFR model outperformed the other developed models in terms of MAPE and MAE, while the GB model achieved the lowest MedAE. Both RFR and GB models achieved the lowest RMSE. The developed models are expected to support decision-makers in accurately predicting the condition rating of concrete bridge decks to prioritize maintenance and rehabilitation decisions.

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